

Androgen Receptor Expression and Prognosis in Estrogen Receptor–Positive, HER2-Negative Invasive Ductal Breast Cancer: A Retrospective Longitudinal Cohort from a Specialized Breast Cancer Center (2010–2024)

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To determine androgen receptor (AR) expression and evaluate its association with disease-free survival (DFS), overall survival (OS), and clinicopathologic characteristics in patients with estrogen receptor–positive (ER+), HER2-negative invasive ductal breast cancer.

Methods: Retrospective, longitudinal, observational study conducted at a specialized breast disease institute. From a database of 293 ER+ / HER2-negative patients diagnosed between 2010–2014 and followed through October 31, 2024, 87 eligible patients with available tumor tissue were included (clinical stage IIA–IIIC). AR expression was assessed by immunohistochemistry and categorized as positive when nuclear staining exceeded 10% of tumor cells. Clinicopathologic variables and treatments were compared by AR status. DFS and OS were estimated using Kaplan–Meier curves and compared using log-rank tests. Prognostic factors were explored using univariate Cox proportional hazards models.

Results: AR was positive in 78/87 patients (89.7%) and negative in 9/87 (10.3%). No significant differences were observed between AR-positive and AR-negative groups regarding age, menopausal status, clinical stage, pathologic stage, tumor size, nodal status, grade, lymphovascular invasion, luminal subtype, or treatment patterns. AR expression was not associated with DFS (log-rank $p = 0.698$) or OS (log-rank $p = 0.868$). In univariate Cox analysis for DFS, age group (HR 0.574; $p = 0.023$), ovarian function status (HR 2.977; $p = 0.038$), and clinical tumor size (HR 3.130; $p = 0.024$) were prognostic; no variables were prognostic for OS.

Conclusions: In this ER+ / HER2-negative cohort, AR expression was highly prevalent but was not significantly associated with DFS or OS. Recurrence risk appeared more strongly influenced by age, ovarian function status, and tumor size than by AR expression.

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INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is the most commonly diagnosed cancer in women worldwide and remains a leading cause of cancer-related mortality. Global estimates have reported approximately 1.7 million new cases annually and more than 500,000 deaths, underscoring its major public health burden. (1) In the United States, millions of women live with breast cancer, and lifetime risk remains high. (2,3) Despite substantial improvements in outcomes—reflected in high 5-year survival in contemporary series—mortality reductions

have been attributed to advances in screening and systemic therapy. (4,5)

In Mexico, breast cancer incidence and mortality have increased over recent decades, influenced by demographic aging, lifestyle shifts, and persistent barriers to timely diagnosis. (6,7) Socioeconomic disparities contribute to later-stage presentation and higher mortality, and national reports indicate that a large proportion of patients are still diagnosed at locally advanced stages. (8–10)

Breast cancer is biologically heterogeneous. Modern classification integrates histopathology and molecular

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phenotype to guide prognosis and therapy. (11) Clinical and pathologic staging—formalized in contemporary staging systems—remains central to treatment planning and risk stratification. (12) Histologic type and grade further contribute to prognostication, and contemporary overviews emphasize the integration of clinicopathologic and biomarker features. (13,14)

Hormone receptor signaling drives the majority of breast cancers. Androgen receptor (AR) is expressed across breast cancer subtypes and is frequently co-expressed in ER-positive tumors. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses have suggested that AR expression may be associated with outcomes in early breast cancer, although findings vary by subtype and analytic approach. (15) In parallel, antiandrogen therapies developed for prostate cancer have renewed interest in AR as a potentially actionable target. (16) Current guidelines focus on established biomarkers for screening/diagnosis and routine clinical decision-making, and AR assessment is not yet standard in routine breast cancer workups. (17) Nonetheless, immunohistochemistry can quantify AR expression, and AR has been proposed as a prognostic and predictive biomarker. (18)

Mechanistically, AR is a nuclear steroid receptor that modulates transcription through ligand-dependent activation and interaction with intracellular signaling pathways. (19) Preclinical studies suggest that androgens can suppress proliferation in ER+ / AR+ breast cancer cell models, with effects influenced by pathway crosstalk and receptor context. (20) Molecular studies have shown functional interactions between ER and AR that may alter ER transactivation and estrogen-driven growth. (21,22) AR has also been implicated in endocrine resistance, including experimental models of tamoxifen resistance. (23)

Clinically, AR expression across breast cancer subtypes has been associated with improved prognosis in several datasets, including meta-analyses and transcriptomic/protein expression studies. (24,25) In ER-positive disease specifically, multiple studies report associations between AR co-expression and more favorable clinicopathologic features and outcomes, though results are not uniform across cohorts. (26,27) Large randomized trial correlative analyses have reported that AR expression may not independently improve

disease-free survival after adjustment, even when AR-positive tumors present with favorable baseline features. (28) Additional evidence suggests that low AR expression may be associated with worse outcomes in hormone receptor–positive disease. (29) In the neoadjuvant setting, AR expression has been linked to lower pathologic complete response rates, with complex relationships to long-term outcomes depending on response. (30) Regarding endocrine therapy, AR/ER signaling balance has been hypothesized to influence tamoxifen resistance, while other studies suggest AR status may differentially relate to outcomes under aromatase inhibitors versus tamoxifen. (31,32)

Given the uncertainty and the limited local data, this study aimed to determine AR expression and evaluate its relationship with prognosis—disease-free survival and overall survival—in patients with ER-positive, HER2-negative breast cancer treated and followed at a specialized breast cancer center.

METHODS

Study design and setting

Exploratory, retrospective, longitudinal, descriptive, observational study conducted at a specialized breast disease institute (FUCAM). The institutional database included 293 patients with ER-positive, HER2-non-overexpressed breast cancer diagnosed between 2010 and 2014 and followed through October 31, 2024.

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria: women ≥ 18 years with invasive ductal carcinoma; ER expression $>1\%$ by immunohistochemistry; HER2 not overexpressed; clinical stage IIA–IIIC; complete clinical record; availability of tumor tissue from core needle biopsy or surgical specimen obtained prior to any neoadjuvant treatment; documentation of recurrence and cause of death where applicable; no second primary malignancy; not pregnant or postpartum; completion of treatment and continued follow-up within the institution.

Exclusion criteria: incomplete treatment according to clinical stage; second primary tumor during treatment or follow-up; death from causes unrelated to breast cancer; pregnancy during treatment or follow-up; insufficient or unavailable tumor tissue.

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Figure 1. Flow diagram of patient selection and distribution by clinical stage and androgen receptor (AR) status.

A total of 293 patients with estrogen receptor–positive, HER2-negative breast cancer diagnosed between 2010 and 2014 were initially identified. Of these, 172 patients were excluded due to failure to meet selection criteria. The remaining 121 patients were considered eligible. After applying exclusion criteria, 34 additional patients were excluded.

A final cohort of 87 patients had adequate tumor tissue available for androgen receptor immunohistochemical analysis. Among these, 78 patients were AR-positive and 9 were AR-negative.

Distribution by clinical stage was as follows:

Stage IIA (n=1): 0 AR-positive, 1 AR-negative

Stage IIB (n=21): 1 AR-positive, 20 AR-negative

Stage IIIA (n=31): 5 AR-positive, 26 AR-negative

Stage IIIB (n=25): 2 AR-positive, 23 AR-negative

Stage IIIC (n=9): 1 AR-positive, 8 AR-negative

The diagram illustrates the progressive reduction of the study population from initial identification to final analysis, as well as the distribution of AR expression across clinical stages.

Sampling and study cohort

A systematic sampling strategy (1 of every 3 patients) was applied to the 293-patient database. Medical record review yielded 121 patients with complete information. Thirty-four were excluded due to bilateral breast cancer, second primary malignancy, loss to follow-up, lack of tissue, or insufficient tissue. Eighty-seven patients had adequate tissue for AR testing and comprised the final analytic cohort.

AR immunohistochemistry and definition

Tumor tissue underwent immunohistochemical staining for AR. AR status was defined by nuclear staining, categorized as:

Positive: >10% tumor cells stained

Negative: ≤10% tumor cells stained

Interpretation was performed by certified pathologists.

Variables and outcomes

Collected variables included age group, ovarian function status (pre/postmenopausal), clinical stage (IIA–IIIC), pathologic stage, clinical and pathologic tumor size categories, axillary nodal involvement (clinical and pathologic), lymphovascular invasion, histologic grade, Ki-67 percentage, ER percentage, luminal subtype (A/B), type of surgery, radiotherapy, neoadjuvant response (pathologic complete response), and endocrine therapy category (tamoxifen, aromatase inhibitor, both, none).

Primary outcomes:

Disease-free survival (DFS): time from surgery to recurrence.

Overall survival (OS): time from surgery to death or last follow-up.

Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed in IBM SPSS Statistics v25. Clinicopathologic variables were compared by AR status using chi-square tests. Given non-normal distributions, Kendall’s Tau-c was used to evaluate associations between AR expression and study variables. DFS and OS were estimated with Kaplan–Meier methods and compared with log-rank tests. Prognostic factors were explored using univariate Cox proportional hazards models. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Patient characteristics and treatments

The study included 87 patients with ER-positive, HER2-negative invasive ductal breast cancer, clinical stage IIA–IIIC. Mean age at diagnosis was 49.22 ± 9.04 years; 40.2% were aged 41–50 years. Premenopausal and postmenopausal status were similarly represented (51.5% vs 48.3%).

Clinical stage distribution: IIA 1.1%, IIB 24.1%, IIIA 35.6%, IIIB 28.7%, IIIC 10.3%. Clinically, 57.4% had tumors >51

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mm; 41.4% had 21–50 mm tumors. Lymphovascular invasion was present in 51.7%. Grade II predominated (74.7%), followed by grade III (23.0%).

All patients received chemotherapy (100%), but pathologic complete response occurred in 10.3%. Most underwent modified radical mastectomy (81.6%). Adjuvant radiotherapy was delivered to 90.8%.

During follow-up, 65.5% had no recurrence. Distant recurrence was observed in 28.7%, regional in 4.6%, and local in 1.1%. Regarding progression, 77.0% had no progression; 20.7% developed distant progression; 2.3% had regional progression. Persistence within 6 months occurred in 2.3%.

AR expression prevalence

AR expression >10% was present in 78/87 patients (89.65%).

AR-negative tumors comprised 9/87 (10.34%).

Association between AR expression and clinicopathologic variables

No statistically significant differences were observed between AR-positive and AR-negative groups across age group ($p = 0.255$), ovarian function ($p = 1.000$), clinical stage ($p = 0.802$), pathologic stage ($p = 0.318$), clinical tumor size ($p = 0.284$), pathologic tumor size ($p = 0.484$), clinical nodal stage ($p = 0.749$), pathologic nodal stage ($p = 0.627$), lymphovascular invasion ($p = 1.000$), tumor grade ($p = 1.000$), luminal subtype ($p = 0.269$), endocrine therapy category ($p = 0.095$), surgery type ($p = 0.668$), radiotherapy ($p = 0.533$), and pathologic complete response ($p = 1.000$). Overall, AR status did not appear to correlate with baseline tumor characteristics or treatment patterns in this cohort.

Prognostic implications of AR expression (DFS and OS)

Kaplan–Meier analysis showed no significant differences by AR expression:

Disease-free survival (DFS):

Overall DFS estimate: 117.620 months (SD \pm 6.805; 95% CI 104.282–130.958)

AR-negative: 116.407 months (SD \pm 15.611; 95% CI 85.810–147.005)

AR-positive: 116.485 months (SD \pm 7.309; 95% CI 102.159–130.812)

Log-rank $p = 0.698$

Overall survival (OS):

Overall OS estimate: 139.842 months (SD \pm 5.283; 95% CI 129.48–150.197)

AR-negative: 124.89 months (SD \pm 13.40; 95% CI 98.619–151.159)

AR-positive: 139.978 months (SD \pm 5.618; 95% CI 128.967–159.989)

Log-rank $p = 0.868$

Although not statistically significant, AR-positive patients showed a directional trend toward fewer recurrences and longer survival compared with AR-negative patients.

Univariate Cox regression

For DFS, the following were prognostic in univariate analysis:

Age group: HR 0.574 (95% CI 0.355–0.927), $p = 0.023$

Ovarian function status: HR 2.977 (95% CI 1.060–8.363), $p = 0.038$

Clinical tumor size: HR 3.130 (95% CI 1.161–8.435), $p = 0.024$

AR positivity was not prognostic for DFS: HR 2.096 (95% CI 0.583–7.533), $p = 0.257$.

No variables were prognostic for OS in univariate analysis, including AR positivity: HR 1.769 (95% CI 0.307–10.182), $p = 0.523$.

Table 1. Clinicopathologic Characteristics According to Androgen Receptor (AR) Expression

Variable	Total (N=87)	AR Positive (n=78, 89.7%)	AR Negative (n=9, 10.3%)	p-value
Mean age (years)	49.22 \pm 9.04	—	—	—
<40	16 (18.4%)	14	2	0.255
41–50	35 (40.2%)	30	5	
51–60	25 (28.7%)	23	2	
61–70	10 (11.5%)	10	0	
>70	1 (1.1%)	1	0	
Premenopausal	45 (51.5%)	40	5	1.000
Postmenopausal	42 (48.3%)	38	4	
Clinical stage				0.802
IIA	1 (1.1%)	1	0	
IIB	21 (24.1%)	20	1	
IIIA	31 (35.6%)	26	5	
IIIB	25 (28.7%)	23	2	
IIIC	9 (10.3%)	8	1	

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Variable	Total (N=87)	AR Positive (n=78, 89.7%)	AR Negative (n=9, 10.3%)	p-value
Grade II	65 (74.7%)	58	7	1.000
Grade III	20 (23%)	18	2	
Lymphovascular invasion present	45 (51.7%)	40	5	1.000
Pathologic complete response	9 (10.3%)	8	1	1.000
Received radiotherapy	79 (90.8%)	71	8	0.533

Table 2. Recurrence and Survival Outcomes by AR Status

Outcome	Total (N=87)	AR Positive	AR Negative	p-value
No recurrence	57 (65.5%)	51	6	0.750
Local recurrence	1 (1.1%)	0	1	
Regional recurrence	4 (4.6%)	4	0	
Distant recurrence	25 (28.7%)	23	2	
No progression	67 (77%)	59	8	0.456
Distant progression	18 (20.7%)	17	1	
Mean DFS (months)	117.62 ± 6.80	116.49 ± 7.31	116.41 ± 15.61	0.698
Mean OS (months)	139.84 ± 5.28	139.98 ± 5.61	124.89 ± 13.40	0.868

Table 3. Univariate Cox Regression Analysis for Disease-Free Survival

Variable	HR	95% CI	p-value
AR positive	2.096	0.583–7.533	0.257
Age group	0.574	0.355–0.927	0.023*
Ovarian function	2.977	1.060–8.363	0.038*
Clinical tumor size	3.130	1.161–8.435	0.024*
Clinical stage	1.636	0.876–3.057	0.123
Lymphovascular invasion	1.093	0.434–2.747	0.851
Tumor grade	0.468	0.159–1.379	0.169

Table 4. Univariate Cox Regression Analysis for Overall Survival

Variable	HR	95% CI	p-value
AR positive	1.769	0.307–10.182	0.523
Age group	0.630	0.305–1.302	0.212
Ovarian function	1.766	0.441–7.070	0.422
Clinical tumor size	3.765	0.666–21.277	0.134
Clinical stage	1.273	0.520–3.117	0.598

DISCUSSION

In this retrospective longitudinal cohort of ER-positive, HER2-negative invasive ductal breast cancer (clinical stage IIA–IIIC), AR expression was highly prevalent (89.7%), consistent with prior reports indicating frequent AR positivity in breast cancer, particularly among ER-positive tumors. (15,18) Despite this high prevalence, AR expression was not significantly associated with DFS or OS, and no clinicopathologic variables differed meaningfully by AR status.

An important characteristic of our cohort is that most patients were diagnosed at advanced clinical stages. Additionally, 85 patients received endocrine therapy, and among them, 75 were treated with tamoxifen. This therapeutic distribution may partially explain the recurrence patterns observed in our study. It is possible that a proportion of patients developed resistance to endocrine therapy, particularly tamoxifen, which could have contributed to higher recurrence rates. Although causality cannot be established in this retrospective analysis, this finding raises relevant clinical questions regarding

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endocrine responsiveness in ER-positive, HER2-negative disease and warrants further investigation.

The prognostic role of AR in early breast cancer has been debated. Meta-analyses and large observational datasets have reported associations between AR expression and improved outcomes across heterogeneous breast cancer populations. (24,25) In ER-positive disease, some cohorts suggest AR co-expression correlates with more favorable tumor biology and improved survival. (26,27) However, large trial-based correlative analyses—particularly in postmenopausal ER-positive populations—have found that AR expression may not independently improve disease-free survival after adjustment, and AR-positive tumors may simply be enriched for favorable baseline features. (28) Our findings align more closely with these latter observations: AR expression was not a significant determinant of prognosis in this dataset.

Importantly, this study identified other factors associated with DFS in univariate analysis: age group, ovarian function status, and clinical tumor size. Older age (particularly above 50 years) was associated with lower recurrence risk ($HR < 1$), whereas postmenopausal status and larger clinical tumor size were associated with increased recurrence risk. These associations are biologically and clinically plausible and reinforce that classical prognostic variables—tumor burden and host endocrine milieu—may outweigh AR status in predicting recurrence within ER-positive disease.

Interestingly, premenopausal patients in our cohort demonstrated lower recurrence rates compared with postmenopausal patients. This observation has not been consistently described in the literature and should therefore be interpreted with caution. One possible hypothesis relates to differences in endocrine therapy response and mechanisms of resistance. Considering experimental evidence suggesting that androgen receptor (AR) signaling may interact with estrogen receptor pathways and potentially influence cellular proliferation, it is plausible that AR expression could play a role in endocrine resistance dynamics. However, this remains speculative and requires validation in larger prospective studies.

The endocrine-therapy implications of AR remain complex. Preclinical evidence shows that AR can modulate ER signaling, including reduction of ER transcriptional activity via receptor interactions and competition for cofactors, which could theoretically influence response to endocrine therapy. (19–22) AR has also been implicated experimentally in tamoxifen resistance. (23) Clinically, however, evidence is mixed: some analyses suggest AR/ER balance may affect tamoxifen resistance, while other data indicate that AR-negative status may relate to early aromatase inhibitor failure rather than tamoxifen outcomes, and trial datasets have not consistently demonstrated differential benefit by AR status. (31,32) In our cohort, type of endocrine therapy was not significantly associated with AR expression, and AR did not

emerge as a prognostic marker for DFS or OS—findings that argue against using AR

Limitations

This study has several limitations that likely influenced the ability to detect prognostic effects. First, the AR-negative subgroup was small ($n = 9$), limiting statistical power and widening confidence intervals, especially in survival analyses. Second, the cohort reflects a selected subset with available tumor tissue and complete follow-up at a single specialized center, potentially introducing selection bias. Third, while the study used established survival methods and Cox modeling, only univariate hazard ratios are available here; without robust multivariable models, residual confounding cannot be excluded. Finally, AR was assessed using a $>10\%$ cut-off; alternative thresholds (e.g., $\geq 1\%$) used in some studies may yield different categorizations.

Clinical implications and future directions

Despite high AR prevalence, AR expression did not significantly stratify DFS or OS in this ER-positive / HER2-negative cohort. Future studies should prioritize larger cohorts (especially increasing AR-negative representation), standardized AR scoring and cut-offs, and multivariable models adjusting for stage, grade, Ki-67, nodal status, and treatment. Prospective trials would be needed to determine whether AR-targeted strategies offer clinically meaningful benefit in ER-positive disease beyond established endocrine approaches. (16,30)

CONCLUSIONS

In this cohort of estrogen receptor–positive, HER2-negative breast cancer, androgen receptor (AR) expression was highly prevalent ($\sim 89\%$). AR expression was not significantly associated with clinicopathologic characteristics, disease-free survival, or overall survival. However, age, ovarian function status, and clinical tumor size were associated with disease-free survival.

Patients younger than 50 years experienced a higher recurrence rate. Tumor size also appeared clinically relevant; consistent with prior evidence, larger tumors (particularly >2 cm) are associated with increased recurrence risk in ER-positive disease. Interestingly, premenopausal patients showed lower recurrence in this dataset—an observation that is not commonly reported and should be interpreted cautiously.

We observed that approximately 89% of tumors expressed androgen receptor, which is consistent with previously reported prevalence in ER-positive breast cancer. Nevertheless, this high prevalence constituted a methodological limitation, as the small number of AR-negative cases ($n=9$) significantly limited statistical power for subgroup comparisons. A larger cohort enriched with ER-positive/AR-negative tumors would be necessary to determine whether AR expression exerts a clinically meaningful prognostic effect. Although AR expression did

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not demonstrate a statistically significant prognostic impact, we observed a directional trend toward fewer recurrences among AR-positive patients. Given the very small AR-negative subgroup, the study was underpowered to detect modest differences between groups. Larger studies enriched for ER-positive/AR-negative cases are needed to clarify whether AR contributes to endocrine resistance and whether AR-related signaling influences recurrence risk in specific subgroups.

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